

Bell Collocation Method to Solve High Order Fredholm-Volterra Integro Differential Equations

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Abstract

In this study, a new numerical method has been developed to solve high-order Fredholm-Volterra integro-differential equations under mixed conditions. In this method, Bell polynomials, their derivatives, and collocation points are used to transform the problem into a matrix equation system. When this equation system is solved, approximate solutions are obtained in the form of a truncated Bell series. To demonstrate the reliability and applicability of the numerical method, some numerical examples are provided. These examples are further analyzed based on the residual error function, and the results are examined through tables and graphs.

Keywords: Volterra-Fredholm integro differential equation, Bell polynomial, collocation points, residual error function.

Introduction

Fredholm-Volterra integro-differential equations combine features of both Fredholm integral equations and Volterra integral equations, incorporating derivatives with integrals. These equations arise in describing physical systems with memory, such as heat conduction in materials with memory effects or fluid dynamics, population dynamics and ecology, finance and economics. Analytical solutions to these equations are solved difficult. Therefore numerical method is needed. In recent years, many authors have developed on numerical methods such as Tau method [1,2], Legendre wavelets method [3], Finite Difference Method [4], Haar function method [5], homotopy perturbation method [6], Runge-Kutta Methods [7], Monte Carlo method [8], Bernoulli matrix-collocation method [9], Legendre collocation method [10], Laguerre polynomial method [11], variational iteration method [12], Adomian decomposition method [13] and the methods in [14-19].

In this study, we apply the Bell polynomials method for the following form of Fredholm-Volterra integro-differential equations

$$\sum_{k=0}^m P_k(x)y^{(k)}(x) = g(x) + \int_a^b K_f(x,t)y^{(r)}(t)dt + \int_0^x K_v(x,t)y^{(s)}(t)dt \quad a \leq x, t \leq b \quad (1)$$

under the initial boundary conditions

$$\sum_{k=0}^{m-1} (a_{jk}y^{(k)}(a) + b_{jk}y^{(k)}(b)) = \lambda_j, j = 0,1,2, \dots, m-1. \quad (2)$$

where $P_k(x)$, $g(x)$, $K_f(x,t)$ and $K_v(x,t)$ continuous functions in $[a,b]$, λ_j , a_{jk} and b_{jk} are real constant coefficients, $y(x)$ is an unknown solution function.

The goal is to find an approximate solution to Equation (1) by expressing it in terms of Bell polynomials as

$$y(x) \cong y_N(x) = \sum_{n=0}^N a_n B_n(x), N \geq m \quad (3)$$

where a_n , $n = 0,1, \dots, N$ are unknown Bell coefficients and the Bell polynomials $B_n(x)$ where $n = 0,1, \dots, N$ are defined by

$$B_n(x) = \sum_{k=0}^n S(n,k)x^k \quad (4)$$

where

$$S(n,k) = \sum_{j=0}^k \frac{(-1)^{k-j}}{k!} \binom{k}{j} j^n$$

are Stirling numbers of the second kind [20-23].

Matrix Relations

Fundamental Matrix Relations

Let us write Equation (1) in the form

$$D(x) = g(x) + I_f(x) + I_v(x) \tag{5}$$

where the differential part is

$$D(x) = \sum_{k=0}^m P_k(x)y^{(k)}(x)$$

Fredholm integral part is

$$I_f(x) = \int_a^b K_f(x, t)y^{(r)}(t)dt$$

and Volterra integral part is

$$I_v(x) = \int_0^x K_v(x, t)y^{(s)}(t)dt$$

We transform these components and mixed conditions (2) into their corresponding matrix forms in the sections that follow.

Matrix Relations for Differential Part

First of all, we can write the Bell polynomials defined in Equation (4) $B(x)$ in the matrix form

$$B(x) = X(x)S \tag{6}$$

where

$$B(x) = [B_0(x) \ B_1(x) \ \dots \ B_N(x)] \ , \ X(x) = [1 \ x \ x^2 \ \dots \ x^N]$$

and

$$S = \begin{bmatrix} S(0,0) & S(1,0) & S(2,0) & \dots & S(N,0) \\ 0 & S(1,1) & S(2,1) & \dots & S(N,1) \\ 0 & 0 & S(2,2) & \dots & S(N,2) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & S(N,N) \end{bmatrix}$$

We consider the approximate solution $y(x)$ of Equation (1) matrix form as [24]

$$y(x) \cong y_N(x) = B(x)A \tag{7}$$

and its k th derivative becomes

$$y^{(k)}(x) = B^{(k)}(x)A \tag{8}$$

By substituting (6) into (7) we obtain

$$y(x) \cong y_N(x) = X(x)SA \tag{9}$$

On the other hand its clearly seen [25] the relation between $X(x)$ and its derivatives $X^k(x)$ is

$$\begin{aligned} X^{(1)}(x) &= X(x)M \\ X^{(2)}(x) &= X^{(1)}(x)M = X(x)M^2 \\ X^{(3)}(x) &= X^{(2)}(x)M = X(x)M^3 \\ &\vdots \\ X^{(k)}(x) &= X^{(k-1)}(x)M = X(x)M^k \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

where

$$M = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & N \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \end{bmatrix} , M^0 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

By substituting the matrix form (9)-(10) into (8) we get the following matrix relation

$$y^{(k)}(x) \cong y_N^{(k)}(x) = B^{(k)}(x)A = X^{(k)}(x)SA = X(x)M^kSA \tag{11}$$

By substituting the relation (11) into Equation (5), we obtain the matrix relation for differential part

$$D(x) = \sum_{k=0}^m P_k(x)X(x)M^kSA \tag{12}$$

Matrix Relations for Fredholm Integral Part and Volterra Integral Part

The matrix representation of the Kernel functions $K_f(x, t)$ and $K_v(x, t)$ in Equation (1) are realized as follows

$$K_f(x, t) = \mathbf{B}(x)\mathbf{K}_f\mathbf{B}^T(t) \quad \text{and} \quad K_v(x, t) = \mathbf{B}(x)\mathbf{K}_v\mathbf{B}^T(t) \tag{13}$$

where $\mathbf{K}_f = \mathbf{K}_v = \mathbf{K} = [k_{pq}]$ and the truncated Maclaurin series of the kernel function $K_f(x, t)$ and $K_v(x, t)$ in the form

$$K(x, t) = \sum_{p=0}^N \sum_{q=0}^N k_{pq} x^p t^q$$

where

$$k_{pq} = \frac{1}{p!q!} \frac{\partial^{p+q} K(0,0)}{\partial x^p \partial t^q}, \quad p, q = 0, 1, \dots, N.$$

By substituting (9) into the Equation (13) we get Fredholm integral part is

$$I_f(x) = \int_a^b K_f(x, t)y^{(r)}(t)dt = \int_a^b \mathbf{X}(x)\mathbf{K}_f\mathbf{X}^T(t)\mathbf{X}(t)\mathbf{M}^r\mathbf{S}\mathbf{A} dt = \mathbf{X}(x)\mathbf{K}_f\mathbf{Q}\mathbf{M}^r\mathbf{S}\mathbf{A} \tag{14}$$

where

$$\mathbf{Q} = \int_a^b \mathbf{X}^T(t)\mathbf{X}(t)dt = [k_{pq}], \quad k_{pq} = \frac{b^{p+q+1} - a^{p+q+1}}{p+q+1}, \quad p, q = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N.$$

Similarly Volterra integral part is

$$I_v(x) = \int_a^x K_v(x, t)y^{(s)}(t)dt = \int_a^x \mathbf{X}(x)\mathbf{K}_v\mathbf{X}^T(t)\mathbf{X}(t)\mathbf{M}^s\mathbf{S}\mathbf{A} dt = \mathbf{X}(x)\mathbf{K}_v\boldsymbol{\theta}(x)\mathbf{M}^s\mathbf{S}\mathbf{A} \tag{15}$$

where

$$\boldsymbol{\theta}(x) = [\varphi_{ij}(x)] = \int_a^x \mathbf{X}^T(t)\mathbf{X}(t)dt, \quad \varphi_{ij}(x) = \frac{x^{i+j+1} - a^{i+j+1}}{i+j+1}; \quad i, j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N.$$

Matrix relation for the conditions

The matrix form of the conditions Equation (2) is written using relations (9)

$$\sum_{k=0}^{m-1} (a_{jk}\mathbf{X}(a)\mathbf{M}^k\mathbf{S} + b_{jk}\mathbf{X}(b)\mathbf{M}^k\mathbf{S}) = \lambda_j, \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, m-1. \tag{16}$$

Bell Collocation Method

The matrix relation (11), (14) and (15) can be written Equation (1), the following matrix equation is obtained

$$\sum_{k=0}^m P_k(x)\mathbf{X}(x)\mathbf{M}^k\mathbf{S}\mathbf{A} = g(x) + \mathbf{X}(x)\mathbf{K}_f\mathbf{Q}\mathbf{M}^r\mathbf{S}\mathbf{A} + \mathbf{X}(x)\mathbf{K}_v\boldsymbol{\theta}(x)\mathbf{M}^s\mathbf{S}\mathbf{A} \tag{17}$$

The collocation points x_i are defined as

$$x_i = a + \frac{b-a}{N}i, \quad i = 0, 1, \dots, N. \tag{18}$$

By using the collocation points (18) into Equation (17) we obtain the system of the matrix equations

$$\sum_{k=0}^m P_k(x_i)\mathbf{X}(x_i)\mathbf{M}^k\mathbf{S}\mathbf{A} = g(x_i) + \mathbf{X}(x_i)\mathbf{K}_f\mathbf{Q}\mathbf{M}^r\mathbf{S}\mathbf{A} + \mathbf{X}(x_i)\mathbf{K}_v\boldsymbol{\theta}(x_i)\mathbf{M}^s\mathbf{S}\mathbf{A} \tag{19}$$

or briefly fundamental matrix equation

$$\underbrace{\left\{ \sum_{k=0}^m \mathbf{P}_k \mathbf{X} \mathbf{M}^k \mathbf{S} - \mathbf{X} \mathbf{K}_f \mathbf{Q} \mathbf{M}^r \mathbf{S} - \lambda \overline{\mathbf{X} \mathbf{K}_v \boldsymbol{\theta} \mathbf{M}^s \mathbf{S}} \right\}}_w \mathbf{A} = \mathbf{G} \tag{20}$$

where

$$\mathbf{P}_k = \begin{bmatrix} P_k(x_0) & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & P_k(x_1) & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & P_k(x_N) \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{X} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & x_0 & \dots & x_0^N \\ 1 & x_1 & \dots & x_1^N \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 1 & x_N & \dots & x_N^N \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{K}_f = \begin{bmatrix} k_{00} & k_{01} & \dots & k_{0N} \\ k_{10} & k_{11} & \dots & k_{1N} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ k_{N0} & k_{N1} & \dots & k_{NN} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\overline{\mathbf{K}_v} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K}_v & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \mathbf{K}_v & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & \mathbf{K}_v \end{bmatrix}, \quad \overline{\mathbf{X}} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{X}(x_0) & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \mathbf{X}(x_1) & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & \mathbf{X}(x_N) \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{M} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & N \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\bar{\theta} = \begin{bmatrix} \theta(x_0) & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \theta(x_1) & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & \theta(x_N) \end{bmatrix}, \bar{S} = \begin{bmatrix} S & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & S & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & S \end{bmatrix}, G = \begin{bmatrix} g(x_0) \\ g(x_1) \\ \vdots \\ g(x_N) \end{bmatrix}.$$

The equation (20) can be written as

$$WA = G \text{ or } [W; G] \tag{21}$$

where

$$W = \sum_{k=0}^m P_k X M^k S - X K_f Q M^r S - \lambda \overline{X K_v} \overline{\theta M^s S}.$$

Briefly matrix relation Equation (16) can be written

$$U_j A = [\lambda_j] \text{ or } [U_j ; \lambda_j] \tag{22}$$

where

$$U_j = \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} (a_{jk} X(a) M^k S + b_{jk} X(b) M^k S) = [u_{j0} \quad u_{j1} \quad \dots \quad u_{jN}] \quad j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, m - 1.$$

The *m*th rows from the augmented matrix in form (21) are removed. In their place, the *m*th rows from conditions (23) are inserted. The resulting augmented matrix can be expressed as follows

$$[\widetilde{W}; \widetilde{G}] = \begin{bmatrix} w_{00} & w_{01} & w_{02} & \dots & w_{0N} & ; & g(x_0) \\ w_{10} & w_{11} & w_{12} & \dots & w_{1N} & ; & g(x_1) \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ w_{(N-m)0} & w_{(N-m)1} & w_{(N-m)2} & \dots & w_{(N-m)N} & ; & g(x_{N-m}) \\ u_{00} & u_{01} & u_{02} & \dots & u_{0N} & ; & \lambda_0 \\ u_{10} & u_{11} & u_{12} & \dots & u_{1N} & ; & \lambda_1 \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ u_{(m-1)0} & u_{(m-1)1} & u_{(m-1)2} & \dots & u_{(m-1)N} & ; & \lambda_{m-1} \end{bmatrix} \tag{23}$$

If $rank(\widetilde{W}) = rank[\widetilde{W}; \widetilde{G}] = (N + 1)$, then we can write

$$A = (\widetilde{W})^{-1} \widetilde{G}.$$

Consequently, the matrix **A** (which represents the unknown Bell coefficients) is uniquely determined by Equation (1). This unique solution can be represented using a truncated Bell series.

Error Estimation

The exact solution *y(x)* and the approximate solution *y_N(x)* are given. The error function *e_N* is calculated as follows

$$e_N = y(x) - y_N(x). \tag{24}$$

The residual function of numerical method is defined [26,27]

$$R_N(x) = L[y_N(x)] - g(x) \tag{25}$$

where

$$L[y_N(x)] = \sum_{k=0}^m P_k(x) y_N^{(k)}(x) - \int_a^b K_f(x, t) y_N^{(r)}(t) dt - \int_0^x K_v(x, t) y_N^{(s)}(t) dt = g(x) + R_N(x).$$

Now, by subtracting (24) and (2) into (25) the error problem is expressed in the following form

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \sum_{k=0}^m P_k(x) e_N^{(k)}(x) - \int_a^b K_f(x, t) e_N^{(r)}(t) dt - \int_0^x K_v(x, t) e_N^{(s)}(t) dt &= -R_N(x). \\ \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} \left(a_{jk} e_N^{(k)}(a) + b_{jk} e_N^{(k)}(b) \right) &= 0 \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, m - 1. \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{26}$$

By applying the numerical method to equation (26), the approximation *e_{N,M}(x)* to *e_N* is acquired. This approximation represents the error function based on the residual function *R_N(x)*. The corrected Bell polynomial solution is then given by *y_{N,M}(x) = y_N(x) + e_{N,M}(x)*. Consequently, the estimated error function yields the following corrected Bell error function as

$$E_{N,M}(x) = e_N(x) - e_{N,M}(x) = y_N(x) - y_{N,M}(x).$$

Numerical Examples

Example 1. Consider the linear Fredholm Volterra integro differential equation

$$y''(x) + xy'(x) - 2y(x) = -\frac{x^3}{3} + x^2 + \frac{11}{12}x + \int_0^1 xty(t)dt + \int_0^x y(t)dt$$

with the initial conditions

$$y(0) = 1, y'(0) = -2.$$

The exact solution of the problem is $y(x) = (x - 1)^2$. For N = 2 is computed as

$$\left\{x_0 = 0, x_1 = \frac{1}{2}, x_2 = 1\right\}$$

and using Equation (20) fundamental matrix equation of the problem is

$$\{P_0XS + P_1XMS + P_2XM^2S - XK_fQS - \overline{XK}_v\overline{\theta S}\}A = G$$

where

$$P_0 = \begin{bmatrix} -2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -2 \end{bmatrix}, P_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, P_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, G = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 2 \\ \frac{3}{3} \\ \frac{19}{12} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$M = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, S = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, X = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & \frac{1}{2} & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$Q = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{3} \\ \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{3} & \frac{1}{4} \\ \frac{1}{3} & \frac{1}{4} & \frac{1}{5} \end{bmatrix}, \overline{X} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{4} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \overline{\theta} = \begin{bmatrix} \theta(0) & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \theta(\frac{1}{2}) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \theta(1) \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\overline{K}_v = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, K_f = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

The augmented matrix for fundamental matrix equation is found as

$$[W: G] = \begin{bmatrix} -2 & 0 & 2 & 0 \\ 11 & 19 & 25 & 2 \\ -\frac{4}{4} & -\frac{24}{24} & \frac{24}{24} & \frac{3}{3} \\ 7 & 11 & 5 & 19 \\ -\frac{2}{2} & -\frac{6}{6} & -\frac{12}{12} & \frac{12}{12} \end{bmatrix}.$$

Using Equation (16) the conditions calculated

$$[U_0; \lambda_0] = [1 \ 0 \ 0 \ ; \ 1] \text{ and } [U_1; \lambda_1] = [0 \ 1 \ 1 \ ; \ -2].$$

The new augmented matrix becomes

$$[\overline{W}; \overline{G}] = \begin{bmatrix} -2 & 0 & 2 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & -2 \end{bmatrix}.$$

By solving the system $[\tilde{W}; \tilde{G}]$ the coefficients matrix is found as $A = [1 \quad -3 \quad 1]^T$. Finally, by substituting the obtained Bell coefficients A Equation (3) the exact solution of problem is obtained

$$y(x) = (x - 1)^2.$$

Example 2. [28] Consider the linear Fredholm Volterra integro differential equation

$$y'(x) = 2 \exp(x) - 2 + \int_0^1 y(t)dt + \int_0^x y(t)dt$$

with the initial condition $y(0) = 0$. The exact solution of the problem is $y(x) = x \exp(x)$. For $N = 5, M = 6$ and $N = 14, M = 15$ approximated solutions and corrected Bell solutions are given in Table 1. The values of the error estimation are given Figure 1 and Figure 2.

Table 1. Exact solution, Bell solution and corrected Bell solutions for Example 2

Exact solution		Bell Solution $y_N(x)$		Corrected Bell Solution $y_{N,M}(x)$	
x_i		$N = 5$	$N = 14$	$N = 5, M = 6$	$N = 14, M = 15$
0	0	0	0	0	0
0.2	0.2442805516	0.244273563	0.2442805516	0.2442820688	0.2442805516
0.4	0.5967298791	0.5967371107	0.596729879	0.596732169	0.5967298791
0.6	1.09327128	1.093277646	1.09327128	1.093274517	1.09327128
0.8	1.780432743	1.780508193	1.780432743	1.780438758	1.780432743
1	2.718281828	2.718509148	2.718281829	2.718298662	2.718281828

Figure 1. The comparison of $|e_5|$, $|e_{5,6}|$ and $|E_{5,6}|$ of the Example 2

Figure 2. The comparison of $|e_{14}|$, $|e_{14,15}|$ and $|E_{14,15}|$ of the Example 2

Conclusion

High-order Fredholm-Volterra integro-differential equations are difficult to solve. In this article, a new numerical method based on Bell polynomials has been developed to solve Fredholm-Volterra integro-differential equations. The applicability of the method was demonstrated by obtaining the exact solution in the first example. Numerical examples were calculated with error analysis based on the residual error function. By observing the obtained results, we confirmed the applicability of the method. Comparisons were made using tables and graphs. Additionally, one of the advantages of the method used is that approximate solutions can be easily calculated using MATLAB. Furthermore, the method can be extended to other types of equations.

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